

PRODUCTION OF ANTI-CORROSION COATING COMPOSITIONS ON THE BASIS OF MODIFIED UREA-FORMALDEHID OLGYMERS. STUDY OF ADHESION ABILITY OF COVER COMPOSITIONS ON THE BASIS OF MODIFIED UREA-FORMALDEHID OLIGOMERS

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Abstract

Urea-formaldehyde oligomer was modified with phenolomonomaleinamide in different proportions (1, 2, 3%) to form coating compositions. The adhesion and physical-mechanical properties of the prepared compositions at different temperatures were studied and compared with the properties of the composition based on the unmodified oligomer.

Keywords: urea-formaldehyde oligomer, phenolomonomaleinamide, modification, composition, adhesion, physical and mechanical properties

Introduction

The coating of substrates with polymer-based coatings in various fields has aroused significant interest. Depending on their purpose, these coatings are resistant to corrosion, aggressive environments, corrosion, decorative, etc. used for purposes such as. Epoxy oligomers, phenol-formaldehyde oligomers, urea-formaldehyde oligomers, etc. are mainly used in the synthesis of coating compositions it is used. [1]

Urea-formaldehyde oligomers are thermoreactive polymers formed by the polycondensation of urea and formaldehyde. Due to the low cost and ease of the synthesis process and the wide range of applications, it is widely used in various sectors of the economy.

One of the main reasons for the use of these oligomers is their high adhesion. The presence of this feature has increased the suitability for use in the technology of obtaining coatings based on them. However, one of the disadvantages of urea-formaldehyde oligomers is that they are not water resistant. [2]

In order to improve this property, it is necessary to modify urea-formaldehyde resins. Phenolomonomaleinamide was taken as a modifier. The choice of this modifier is due to the fact that it has previously been used in coatings with high deformation resistance and thermal properties.

Phenolomonomaleinamide is a compound with functional groups such as active amine and phenyl. These functional groups interact with both the functional groups of the urea-formaldehyde resin and the active centers of the substrate during the formation of the coating and lead to the formation of a dense mesh structure. [3, 4]

Experimental part

The degree of solidification of the modified urea-formaldehyde oligomer was studied at temperatures of 60, 100, 120, 1400C (Table 1). The results of the obtained compositions were compared, and based on the results of the research, it was determined that the adhesion strength showed the highest results when adding a modifier up to 2% of the dry residual mass of the oligomer.

Table 1.

The amount of modifier in the production of modified urea-formaldehyde oligomer.

№	Components	I	II	III	IV
1	Urea-formaldehyde, %	100	99	98	97
2	Phenolomonomaleinamide,%	-	1	2	3
Total		100	100	100	100

Results and its discussion

Based on the results obtained, graphical curves of changes in adhesion strength depending on temperature were constructed. (Figure 1-4)

First, a temperature-dependent graph of the adhesion strength of the modified urea-formaldehyde oligomer was developed to determine the extent to which the amount of modifier affected the adhesion of the composition. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of the adhesion of the composition on the basis of unmodified oligomer (I)

Comparing the temperature dependence of the adhesion capacity of the second composition with the first composition, we see that the adhesion strength increased by 2.8 MPa at a temperature of 60 °C. This is due to the increased adhesion due to the large number

of functional groups. Due to the acceleration of the structuring process with increasing temperature, the adhesion capacity began to decrease as functional groups participated in the construction process. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. II adhesion strength of the composition temperature dependence

Comparing the adhesion strength of the III composition with the composition based on urea formaldehyde oligomer, we see that the adhesion strength increased to 4.0 MPa. Due to the increase in the amount

of modifier per unit surface, the adhesion properties increased. As the temperature increases, the interaction between the functional groups increases, so the construction takes place and the adhesion strength decreases sharply. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. III adhesion strength of the composition temperature dependence

At all temperatures in the IV composition, the decrease in adhesion strength compared to the II and III components, along with the construction process, the

adhesion strength decreased due to the destruction of the composition as the temperature increased. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. IV adhesion strength of the composition temperature dependence

As a result, we can say that when the content of phenolomonaleinamide is 2% and hardened in the temperature range of 60 – 100 °C, it is possible to obtain a coating composition with high adhesion and physical and mechanical properties.

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